

Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with Substituted Thiocarbamides

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Sixteen complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) have been synthesised using *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-*N'*-phenyl, *N*-*N'*-di-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl), *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenyl and *N*-*o*-carboxyphenyl thiocarbamides as ligands and characterised on the basis of analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, i.r. and electronic spectral studies. Complexes have the composition $[ML_2]$. ($M = \text{Co(II)}$, $[MLCl(H_2O)_2]$ ($M = \text{Ni(II)}$), $[MLCl]$ ($M = \text{Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II)}$).

THIOUREA has been used extensively as a ligand to study the affinity of the sulfur atom towards different metal ions. Many simple complexes of thiourea¹⁻³ and mixed ligand complexes⁴⁻⁶ containing thiourea and nitrogen donor ligands have been reported earlier. Even though less number of complexes with substituted thiourea as ligands have been investigated^{7,8}, Zn(II) and Hg(II) compounds have been well studied. In spite of the extensive work in this field, attempts have not been made to study complexes of thiocarbamide ligands containing other potential donor sites (*viz* oxygen or nitrogen) in addition to the sulfur atom. It was, therefore thought worthwhile to synthesise some new substituted thiocarbamides and study their complexation behaviour towards a series of divalent metal ions. In an earlier communication⁹, we reported complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Hg(II) with a hydroxy and carboxy substituted thiocarbamide. This communication presents a number of complexes of *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-*N'*-phenyl and *N*-*N'*-di-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl) thiocarbamide with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) ions and complexes of *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenyl and *N*-*o*-carboxyphenyl thiocarbamide with Cu(II) and Cd(II) ions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-*N'*-phenyl thiocarbamide :

To an ethanolic solution of *o*-aminophenol (4.36 g), phenyl isothiocyanate (5.40 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 15 minutes over a water-bath. On cooling, crystalline compound of the corresponding thiocarbamide separated out which was then filtered, washed in ethanol and dried in *vacuo*.

Preparation of *N*-*N'*-di-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl) thiocarbamide :

To an ethanolic solution of *o*-aminophenol (4.36 g.), carbondisulphide (3 ml) and potassium hydroxide (2 g.) were added and refluxed for half an hour over waterbath, and then the hot solution was poured into ice-cold water. Then the hot solution was made slightly acidic by adding conc. HCl, when reddish-brown precipitate was separated out which was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from rectified spirit.

The synthesis of *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenyl and *N*-*o*-carboxyphenyl thiocarbamide has been described in our earlier communication⁹.

Preparation of complexes :

Ethanolic solution of metallic chlorides were treated with ethanolic solutions of *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-*N'*-phenyl and *N*-*N'*-di-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl) thiocarbamides and ethanolic solution of Cu(II), Cd(II), chlorides were treated with *N*-*o*-hydroxyphenyl and *N*-*o*-carboxyphenyl thiocarbamides in the dimethyl formamide in stoichiometric ratios followed by the dropwise addition of ammoniac when metal chelates separated out which were then filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*.

Metals, nitrogen and sulfur in the complexes were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution of the complexes using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens by Gouy method using $\text{Co}[\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. IR spectra were measured on KBr phase by a Perkin Elmer-221 spectrophotometer in the 200-4000 cm^{-1} range. Electronic spectra were recorded in M/100 chloroform solution of the

complexes using Hilger-Watt Uvispeck spectrometer. Analytical data are recorded in Table-1 and spectral data in Table-2.

IR spectra have been of considerable help in determining the bonding sites. There are three bonding sites very near to each other, viz. the hydroxyl or

TABLE-1 ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Compound	% of metal		% of N		% of S		Δ mhos cm ²	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.		
[CoL ₂]	10.38	10.77	10.03	10.23	11.48	11.70	8.0	5.00
[CoL' ₂]	9.85	10.23	9.57	9.80	10.93	11.20	7.5	5.10
[NiLCl (H ₂ O) ₂]	14.95	15.37	7.16	7.33	8.21	8.33	8.0	3.10
[NiL'Cl (H ₂ O) ₂]	14.72	15.09	7.14	7.23	8.08	8.21	8.5	3.00
[CuLCl]	18.14	18.55	7.92	8.17	9.17	9.34	8.2	1.81
[CuL'Cl]	17.67	17.92	7.64	7.09	8.87	9.02	10.1	1.83
[CuL''Cl]	23.62	23.88	10.27	10.49	11.72	11.99	7.8	1.78
[ZnLCl]	21.18	21.58	9.36	9.50	10.60	10.86	7.5	1.81
[ZnL'Cl]	18.52	18.98	7.97	8.13	9.14	9.29	9.6	-
[ZnL''Cl]	17.94	18.25	7.69	7.84	8.54	8.82	8.8	-
[CdLCl]	28.28	28.71	6.94	7.15	7.93	8.17	11.5	-
[CdL'Cl]	27.45	27.86	6.79	6.94	7.68	7.93	8.8	-
[CdL''Cl]	35.21	35.63	8.59	8.87	8.93	10.14	9.4	-
[HgLCl]	29.94	30.13	7.25	7.49	8.36	8.57	11.2	-
[HgL'Cl]	41.46	41.32	5.54	5.87	6.32	6.67	9.2	-
[HgL''Cl]	40.53	40.86	5.47	5.69	6.37	6.51	9.5	-

TABLE-2 IR AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	ν (C-O)	ν (C-S)	ν (M-O)	ν (M-N)	ν (M-S)	ν (M-Cl)	ν_{max} K. K.(e)
[CoL ₂]	1240	1090	460	375	270	-	20.9(18), 18.9(29), 18.0(16)
[CoL' ₂]	1250	1100	450	380	260	-	20.8(18), 19.0(30), 7.9(15)
[NiLCl (H ₂ O) ₂]	1240	1095	440	375	270	230	8.9(7), 13.5(7), 25.2(15)
[NiL'Cl (H ₂ O) ₂]	1250	1090	445	370	265	220	8.9(6), 13.6(6.5), 25.0(16)
[CuLCl]	1245	1085	440	370	275	225	-
[CuL'Cl]	1250	1090	450	375	270	230	-
[CuL''Cl]	1240	1090	440	380	290	230	-
[ZnLCl]	1250	1100	445	370	260	220	-
[ZnL'Cl]	1245	1045	420	360	260	225	-
[ZnL''Cl]	1255	1100	425	370	270	230	-
[CdLCl]	1250	1090	430	380	270	230	-
[CdL'Cl]	1245	1085	420	375	280	230	-
[CdL''Cl]	1240	1100	425	370	280	235	-
[HgLCl]	1240	1100	460	375	275	220	-
[HgL'Cl]	1250	1095	455	380	260	225	-

LH = N-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-N'-phenyl thiocarbamide, L'H = N,N'-di(*o*-hydroxyphenyl) thiocarbamide, L''H = N-*o*-hydroxyphenyl thiocarbamide, L''H' = N-*o*-carboxyphenyl thiocarbamide.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have the composition [ML₂] (M=Co(II), MLCI (H₂O)₂ (M=Ni(II)), [MLCl] (M=Cu(II), Zn(II), Co(II) and Hg(II)). Cobalt complexes are pink, nickel complexes are green, copper complexes are either blue or green and Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes are white. These have fairly low melting points and the conductance values in acetone medium are low indicating nonelectrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic moments (at 25°) of cobalt and nickel complexes show the presence of three and two unpaired electrons respectively indicating a high spin octahedral configuration. Copper complexes are paramagnetic with the presence of one unpaired electron.

carbonyl oxygen, sulfur of the thiocarbonyl group and nitrogen of the amino group. In the ligands the alcoholic C-O vibration occurs around 1250-1260 cm⁻¹, which should usually occur in the 1000-1300 cm⁻¹ range in case of alcohols. In addition, there are both broad and sharp bands in the 3300-3500 cm⁻¹ region due to O-H and N-H stretching vibrations respectively. Usually thiocarbonyl absorption occurs¹⁰ around 1020-1250 cm⁻¹ region, several other bands appear in the 1500-700 cm⁻¹ region due to interaction between C=S and C-N stretching when the C=S group is attached to a nitrogen atom. A prominent sharp band has appeared at ~ 700 cm⁻¹ as in case of simple thiourea.

In case of complexes, C-O and C=S stretching frequencies definitely shift to lower frequency region indicating bonding at these sites. In addition, the position of -NH stretching band also shifts as there is

a splitting when nitrogen is bonded to the metal ion. The broad absorption band due to O-H stretching vibration disappears in case of Co(II), Cu(II) Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes but is observed in case of nickel complexes due to the presence of coordinated water. In complexes with N-N'-di-*o*-hydroxy phenyl thiocarbamide, O-H stretching band is observed in all cases as one -OH group remains free. Evidence in favour of three bonding sites is further substantiated by observations of M-O, M-S and M-N stretching bands in the far infrared spectra of the complexes¹¹. In addition, a low frequency band has been observed around 220-230 cm⁻¹ in case of complexes where halogen is present. Thus from analysis, conductance, and IR spectral studies, Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes are presumably tetraordinated involving a tetrahedral environment around the metal ions.

In the electronic spectra of nickel complexes, three absorption bands appear around 9000, 13000 and 25000 cm⁻¹ region assignable¹² to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (F), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) transitions respectively. Molar absorptivity values are low in conformity with the octahedral configuration of the complexes. Cobalt (II) complexes also exhibit three absorption bands in the 20000, 19000 and 8000 cm⁻¹ region attributable to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ (F) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (P) transitions respectively. Low extinction coefficient values support the octahedral stereochemistry of these

complexes. In the electronic spectra of Cu(II) complexes one broad absorption band appeared around 15000-16000 cm⁻¹ region indicating a planar configuration for these complexes¹².

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